

Effects of continuous improvement on shop-floor employees' job performance in lean production - The role of lean duration

Wickramasinghe, G.L.D.

Department of Textile and Clothing Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Wickramasinghe, V.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

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Abstract

Purpose – The purpose of this paper is to present empirical findings on the effect of continuous improvement (CI) on shop-floor employees' job performance in the lean production system implemented textile and apparel firms.

Design/methodology/approach – A random sample of 657 shop-floor employees full-time engaged in lean production systems implemented textile and apparel firms in Sri Lanka responded for the survey. Statistical methods were used for data analysis.

Findings – It was revealed that CI significantly positively influences shop-floor employees' job performance, and the duration of lean production in operations (termed as lean duration) moderates this relationship.

Originality/value – Investigations on the ways in which CI initiatives influence employees is important in creating an environment to sustain the improvement efforts over a longer period of time. Such lessons would be valuable for academics and practitioners alike worldwide.

Key words continuous improvement, job performance, *Kaizen*, lean production.

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

Continuous improvement (CI), also known as *Kaizen* using Japanese terminology (Hayes, 1981), is seen as “one of the activities whereby processes and procedures are implemented which contribute to organizational goals through the continuous improvement of work processes, work places and work interactions” (Berling, 2000, p. S484). Continuous improvement represents one of the basic tools for adopting a range of process improvement methodologies such as conformance, standardisation, six sigma, lean, balanced scorecard, business excellence models of Malcolm Baldrige, National Quality Award of the respective countries, total quality management, business process re-engineering and Investors in People. The focus of this article is on the implementation of incremental and continual changes to the existing lean production processes aimed at improving job performance of shop-floor employees in textile and apparel firms.

The underlying assumption of CI is that the introduction of incremental and continual changes to the standard way of work will bring about long-lasting changes in the organisation leading to improved performance, survival and growth (Glover et al., 2011; Marin-Garcia et al, 2008; Tanco et al., 2012). Still, continuous improvement initiatives demand endless effort from everyone in the workplace for making improvements of the standard way of work (Malik and YeZhuang, 2006). In the lean production context, employees - especially shop-floor employees - have to accustom to a wide range of new principles, methods, and behavioural routines that radically reshape the way tasks (e.g., materials handling) are carried out at the shop-floor. Hence, researchers such as Losonci et al. (2011) state that employees' views on how new working methods affect them at the shop-floor have become very important in understanding their task performance and immediate work environment. However, we have not come across studies that investigated effects of CI on employees' job performance in the lean production.

Another important concern is how to diffuse lean production concepts within the work organization and sustain the practices over a longer period of time. Although some previous studies provided evidence for the introduction of improvement programs (e.g., Samson et al., 1993), sustainability of the practices was not at satisfactory levels (Sohal et al., 1993). For example, Sohal et al. (1993) provided evidence where improvement initiatives “faded away” or “simply died” few years after the introduction. In this context, investigating the ways in which CI initiatives influence employees is important in understanding how to create an environment to sustain the improvement efforts over a longer period of time. Such lessons would be valuable for academics and practitioners alike worldwide.

In the above context, this paper describes empirical results from an ongoing research study on 1) the effect of CI on shop-floor employees’ job performance, and 2) the role played by the duration of lean production in operation (or lean duration) on the above relationship. Consistent with the objectives, the rest of the article reviews available literature on CI and the effects of CI on job performance. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

2. Literature review

2.1. Continuous improvement

The term CI is referred to a concept in organizational improvement, which is used as one of the basic tools for perfecting process technologies of an organization. Process technologies are sets of ideas involved in the manufacture of a product (or service), sequential steps necessary to combine materials to produce the finished product (or delivery of service), technology associated with the maintenance of the process, and the development of

managerial and organizational capabilities needed to leverage resources optimally (Lall, 1995; Medcof, 2007). As a process technology, perfection is the goal of lean production with constant improvements to the standard way of work. This constant strive for perfection, also known as *Kaizen* in Japan, has now become well known term in other parts of the world. Imai (1986, p. xxix) used the English translation of kaizen as “ongoing improvement involving everyone”.

In broad terms, CI describes a management philosophy in which all employees actively continually seeking out and eliminating sources of process imperfection using a bottom-up approach (Ni and Sun, 2009; Wynder, 2008). Bessant and Caffyn (1997, p. 2) defined CI as “an organisation-wide process of focused and sustained incremental innovation”. Boer et al. (2000, p. xvi) provided the most comprehensive and widely accepted definition, in which CI is the “planned, organised and systematic process of on-going, incremental and company-wide change of existing practices aimed at improving company performance”. According to Boer et al. (2000), the key features of CI are widespread employee involvement, and low risk, cost and investment in the adoption. This definition coincides with previous research that conceptualized CI as a tool for competitive advantage (Berling, 2000; Prado-Prado, 2009; Wilkinson, 2004).

Deming’s (1986) plan-do-check-act (PDCA) repeated cycle and Shewhart’s (1986) plan-do-study-act (PDSA) repeated cycle form the conceptual basis of CI that is practiced currently world-wide. Deming’s (1986) PDCA cycle specifies the importance of gathering data in identifying and defining problems to formulate a plan (plan), implement the plan (do), analyse data to identify the agreement between the original goals and what was actually achieved (check) and take further actions depending on the results (act). In a similar vein, Shewhart’s (1986) PDSA cycle specifies similar stages and aspects emphasised in Deming’s PDCA. These suggest the need of changes in behavioural routines of the organizational

members for the successful adoption of CI (Boer et al., 2000; Bessant and Francis, 1999; Ni and Sun, 2009). Accordingly, CI is best understood by endless churning of Deming's (1986) plan-do-check-act (PDCA) repeated cycle and Shewhart's (1986) plan-do-study-act (PDSA) repeated cycle that emphasize changes to the behavioural routines for sustained incremental organisational change. Behavioural routines obtained from numerous incremental improvements on a process technology can be internalised into the organization by incorporating these into day-to-day operations. Over time, these gradual and incremental transformation of processes and behavioural routines could bring about important and lasting improvements in the organization, such as improvements in productivity (Rapp and Eklund, 2002), quality (Brown et al., 2008), the reduction of production costs (Terziovski and Sohal, 2000) or the time of manufacture (Prado-Prado, 2009).

The present study is conducted in the export-based textile and apparel production industry in Sri Lanka. Owing to rising wages in the labour intensive global export-based textile and apparel industry, production operations shifted from Hong Kong, South Korea, and Taiwan, who were the leaders in the export-based textile and apparel production by the late 1970s, to Sri Lanka, Thailand, Philippines, Indonesia, China, India, and Pakistan. Thereafter, it has, further shifted to other countries with relatively lower labour cost in Asia (such as Laos, Cambodia, Bangladesh, and Vietnam), Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa. Today, export-based textile and apparel producing countries from Asia, Latin and Central America, the Caribbean, Eastern Europe, and North Africa compete intensively with each other for their market share in the global export-based textile and apparel production (for further details Lopez-Acevedo and Robertson, 2016). Since the mid-2000s, in response to increasing labour costs in Sri Lanka, export-based textile and apparel manufacturers identified possibilities for them to turn to lean production for improving the efficiency of production systems. As a basic tool for perfection

in the lean production, firms extensively use CI initiatives in this sector. These initiatives influence the way work is being performed in the shop-floor to become leaner and fitter, and to create a new labour intensive production model that generate distinctive internal capabilities for survival and growth in the international markets.

2.2. Job performance

Job performance is viewed as a key variable in the organizational context (Campbell et al., 1990; Graso and Probst, 2012; Griffin et al., 2007; Pulakos et al., 2000; Varela and Landis, 2010). Campbell et al. (1990) proposed eight job activities to describe job performance in any work context although it is not a must to have all the dimensions in a particular job. These dimensions are job-specific task proficiency, non-job-specific task proficiency, written and oral communication, demonstrating effort, maintaining personal discipline, facilitating performance, supervision and leadership, and administration. Some other researchers such as Pulakos et al. (2000) argued that job performance should represent employees' response to technological advances in the workplace. In a recent study, Graso and Probst (2012) argued that the most important indicators of job performance are quality and quantity. Griffin et al. (2007) argued that in dynamic organizational contexts, job performance should reflect not only proficiency with which an employee carried out job tasks but also the interdependence of work activities and adaptive and proactive behaviour of job holders

When building on the resource-based view of the firm, CI initiatives at work contribute to the performance of firm by leveraging on discretionary effort and desired knowledge, skills, attitudes and the behaviour of its employees (Arthur, 1994). The argument behind this reasoning is that employees' job performance is the direct outcome of how firms manage their workforce, which in turn may contribute to firm performance although the firm

performance is not simply the aggregate of individual job performance (Appelbaum et al., 2000).

The literature agrees that sustained CI has a positive impact on performance improvement while requiring little capital investment (e.g. Boer et al., 2000; Ni and Sun, 2009). Therefore, the ways in which CI initiatives are adopted could have an effect on effort direction, duration and the intensity of employees (Farris et al., 2008). The operations management literature provides evidence for associations between individual level practices and job-level outcomes. For example, positive effects of job enrichment on job performance, team work on job performance, and training on job performance (e.g., Colquitt et al., 2000; Parker and Wall, 1998). In the context of quality management, Turesky and Connell (2010) provided evidence that employees' perceiving CI as a very important part of their job, which leads to positive outcomes in performance. In the context of lean production, Letens et al. (2006) showed that *Kaizen* events have effects on how employees perform work to improve a targeted work area, with specific goals, in an accelerated timeframe (Letens et al., 2006). Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1. CI enhances shop-floor employees' job performance

2.3. Lean duration

Womack and Jones (1996) state that lean manufacturing can only be achieved through time, and lean manufacturing should not be used as a panacea to solve short-term competitive problems. The implementation of lean production systems requires organizations to adapt to new routines, the new methods of work performance, behavioural patterns and changes in organization culture (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996). Previous studies conducted in the textile and apparel sector also supports this argument (Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011a, 2011b, 2012). That is, to build a work environment that is conducive to lean

production naturally demands changes to the social organization of work with new routines, behavioural patterns and fundamental changes in performing work tasks, which require some time to receive acceptance from both shop-floor employees and managers (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1996; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011a, 2011b, 2012). Further, variations could be found in different dimensions based on how long the lean production is in operation (Sohal and Egglestone, 1994; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011a). For instance, when investigating the extent to which lean production has been implemented and what are the structural changes taking place as a result of the implementation within Australian organizations, Sohal and Egglestone (1994) highlighted the importance of collecting data on how long the lean production system is in operation at each firm. Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe (2011a) showed the importance of taking into account the duration of lean production in operation in the lean implemented textile and apparel firms in Sri Lanka.

The literature on CI also supports that time is a critical factor in seeking out and eliminating sources of process imperfection (Bessant and Francis, 1999; Wynder, 2008). For instance, previous researches such as Garvin (1993), Bessant and Francis (1999) and Ni and Sun (2009) state that behavioural routines attached to CI require time to learn and institutionalize. Therefore, *time* can be identified as a key factor in the adoption of new management practices and evaluating the successful spread of concepts, technical information and actual practices within the social system (Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011a). However, our review of the management literature has shown that this information has so far not received the due attention in evaluating CI in lean production operation. In this context, we propose that when investigating the adoption of CI practices, lean duration is an important moderator variable. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H2. Lean duration moderates the relationship between CI and job performance in such a way that the longer the duration, the higher will be job performance.

3. Method

The study was conducted in export-based textile and apparel manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. The following criteria were set in selecting the firms belonging to the study population: 1) A firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) since BOI registered firms should export at least 90 per cent of their output, and 2) A firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and it should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This restriction will isolate firms that had achieved good progress in lean statistics such as work in progress (WIP), first time through (FTT), efficiency of the process, delivery in full on time (DIFOT), accepted quality level (AQL) and cut ship. We identified 14 firms that fulfilled the criteria set for the study that belonging to the Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) 22 and 23 (22 - Textile mill products, 23 - Apparel and other finished products made from fabrics and similar materials). A random sample of 657 shop-floor employees full-time engaged in these 14 firms responded to the survey questionnaire.

With regard to the characteristics of the responding firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1993 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2004. The ownership of all the firms lay with locals. All the firms have adopted lean production methods after 2005, where the latest adoption occurred in two of the firms in the year 2010. On average, these firms had achieved good progress in the implementation of lean with WIP of 35 days, FTT of 70 per cent, efficiency of the process of 90 per cent, DIFOT of 85 per cent, AQL of 91 per cent and cut ship of 90 per cent. When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an

average annual turnover (in US\$) ranging from 80 to 400 million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5,000. All the firms had a dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior-level manager.

With regard to measures, CI was measured by the 7-item scale developed for the study. The item measures of CI are given in Appendix 1. Job performance was measured by the 4-items from Rodwell et al. (1998). Both scales ranged from 1 “Strongly Disagree” to 5 “Strongly Agree” on a five-point Likert response scale. The duration of lean production was assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the years of lean production in operation. Wilks’ Lambda statistic was obtained to check whether any group differences exist among the responses from the 14 firms for the variables of the study. The results of the Wilks’ Lambda statistics for the variables revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) among the responses from the 14 firms.

With regard to methods of data analysis, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were performed. We tested EFA for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias; convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. We conducted CFA using AMOS following Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) recommendation. Accordingly, we assessed CFA results based on normed chi-square (χ^2/df) statistic and fit indices of comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). Hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to test the moderation effect following the recommendations of Fraizer et al. (2004). The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium, and high scores of the variables. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to

determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals.

4. Results and discussion

We first assessed the measures of CI and job performance using EFA procedures. Table 1 provides EFA results for CI. Table 2 provides EFA results for job performance. Second, we assessed measures using CFA procedures. Table 3 summarizes CFA results for CI and job performance separately. Accordingly, the single factor model for CI yielded the fit indices of $\chi^2/df = 2.205$, CFI = .967, TLI = .943 and RMSEA = .017. The single factor model for CI yielded the fit indices of $\chi^2/df = 3.595$, CFI = .943, TLI = .927 and RMSEA = .024. Hence, χ^2/df statistics and fit indices suggested that treating each measure as single factor constructs yielded the best fit for our study. Accordingly, CFA results confirmed the results of EFA.

Table 1 here

Table 2 here

Table 3 here

Table 4 provides descriptive statistics and inter-correlations for the measures in this study. As can be seen, and as expected, correlations between the variables were all statistically significant and in the expected directions. This suggests yielding significant relationships in the direct and moderator analysis.

Table 4 here

The main objectives of the study were to identify the direct effect of CI on shop-floor employees' job performance, and to identify whether lean duration moderates the above direct relationship. We performed moderation analyses based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% CI for the size and significance of the effects. As shown in Table 5 (model 1), CI significantly positively relates to job performance. This supports H1 that CI significantly influence shop-floor employees' job performance. As shown in Table 5 (model 2), lean duration significantly impacts on job performance ($p < 0.001$). The results for the moderator effect of lean duration on manufacturing plant performance are shown in Table 5 (model 3). Accordingly, lean duration moderates the relationships between CI and job performance. This supports H2. Figure 1 illustrates the interaction effects for CI and lean duration on job performance. The interaction effect on job performance is significant at the 95% level of significance, as indicated when the lower and upper levels of the confidence intervals did not include zero.

Table 5 here

Figure 1 here

5. Conclusion and implications

Building on the research gap discussed at the beginning of this article, we investigated how shop-floor employees' job performance could be influenced by *Kaizen*, when organizations continuously improve the way a process technology is utilized, i.e., lean production. The findings showed that CI significantly influences job performance; lean duration moderates this relationship in such a way that the longer the lean duration, the higher will be job

performance. Since it is very rare to find prior empirical studies that investigated CI and job performance within the lean production context, we believe that the findings of our study make unique contributions for both theory and practice.

With regard to implications for the literature, first, the findings revealed the importance of CI in enhancing shop-floor employees' job performance in textile and apparel production. Continuous improvement or *Kaizen* comprised of a series of events or initiatives aimed at improving a targeted work activities, with specific goals, in an accelerated timeframe in the lean production. The results suggest that significant improvements in job performance of employees can be identified as a result of CI. Our findings support the findings of previous studies such as Farris et al. (2008) and Glover et al. (2011) although these are not specific to the textile and apparel sector. Organizations use CI as a tool in lean production for system simplification, waste minimization, and enhance organizational potential to increase their competitiveness in the global market. Any improvements at the shop-floor level are important in this journey with benefits of cost reduction. Therefore, improvements that CI can bring about at shop-floor employees' job performance become important in any context. Especially, business organisations in the developing world practice cost differentiation strategies of market orientation that aim to enter or stabilize in export markets in the West (Ramayah et al., 2011); they may not introduce innovative production practices unless there is a compelling need for survival and growth.

Second, the findings revealed the importance of the duration of lean production in operation in achieving higher levels of job performance. In other words, the study provided empirical data to show that the positive effects of CI on shop-floor employees' job performance is conditioned by the duration of lean production in operation. Organizing manufacturing processes according to lean production requirements demands behaviour that facilitates continuous improvements in the way work is carried out. As stated by Graso and

Probst (2012) and Glover et al. (2011) the number of organisations adopting CI is in the increase. However, previous studies such as Farris et al. (2008) and Glover et al. (2011) provided evidence that many CPI initiatives failed to have expected impact due to issues in managing employees. According to Farris et al. (2008) and Glover et al. (2011) success in specific *Kaizen* event is not sufficient. Organizations need to distinguish between *Kaizen* and *Kaizen events*. Our finding on the moderating role of lean duration also supports this argument. Based on our findings, we could argue that CI will integrate into the lean production work system and achieve highest potential in job performance with the passage of time, i.e., with the increase in the duration of lean production in operation. Hence, we identify this as one of the unique contributions of our study.

Third, the findings of our study have implications for the broader agenda of research in integrating CI with strategic initiatives of lean production. We operationalized different dimensions of CI and job performance, and used multiple parameters to evaluate the situation. The measures we used were empirically based and were shown to be valid and reliable. We believe that the findings of our study provide baseline data that would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. The data analysis did not reveal any significant differences among the firms on our study variables. Therefore, the results can be generalizable. However, future studies are needed from a variety of samples in similar and different contexts.

Fourth, CI requires continuous changes and adapting to new practices by organisational members. Still, CI initiatives operate alongside the command and control structures of conventional management. Therefore, CI initiatives that are aligned with the strategic direction of the firms will guide to design and implement better focused practices for the fulfilment of standard way of work.

Finally, the study has few limitations. This study was designed as a single cross-sectional study using survey methodology. Hence, future research using different research designs, such as longitudinal, could provide more depth to the study context. Further, we investigated one of the aspects that could influence shop-floor employees' job performance in the context of lean production, i.e., CI. In the organizational context, several variables that influence job performance prevail simultaneously, such as propensity to participate in decision making (Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011a), to name one in the textile and apparel production. Future research could design studies to investigate several such variables influencing job performance at a particular point of time.

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Figures

Figure 1. Moderating effect at high and low levels of lean duration

Tables

Table 1: Continuous improvement

Item	Loading
Employees in my organization have high involvement in continuous improvement programs	.807
Continuous improvement programs conducted by my organization are buyer focused	.797
My organization has mechanisms for evaluating manufacturing processes	.788
Senior management has high involvement and support for continuous improvement programs	.760
My organization has a culture open to continuous improvements	.729
My organization has continuous improvement system which is integrated to strategic goals and objectives	.723
My organization follows best practices of continuous improvement available in the industry	.702
Cronbach's alpha	.742
AVE	.58
Construct reliability	.90

Table 2. Job performance

Item	Loading
I am currently working at the best performance level	.856
I am always appreciated for the quality of my work	.851
I am the fastest at the work I do	.737
I am willing to expend extra effort when it is needed	.716
Cronbach's alpha	.744
AVE	.63
Construct reliability	.87

Table 3. CFA results for measures of CI and job performance

Measure	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
1-factor CI	2.205	.967	.943	.017
1-factor job performance	3.595	.943	.927	.024

Table 4. Construct correlation matrix

	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1 CI	4.17	.57	.76		
2 Job performance	4.02	.46	.474**	.79	
3 Lean duration	1.49	.40	.259**	.201**	-

Notes: ** p < 0.01; diagonal entries, square root of AVE where appropriate; off-diagonal entries, correlation between constructs

Table 5. Hierarchical regression analysis

	Model 1 B	Model 2 B	Model 3 B
<i>Step 1: Independent</i>			
CI	.488***	.475***	.802***
<i>Step 2: Moderator</i>			
Lean duration		.219***	.340***
<i>Step 3: Interaction term</i>			
CI x Lean duration			.179***
R ²	.225***	.227***	.244***
R ² (Adj.)	.223***	.224***	.241***

Note: *** p < .001; Standard errors for the variables were less than .45; Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; Bootstrap sample size = 5,000.

Appendix 1 – Item measures

Continuous improvement:

Employees in my organization have high involvement in continuous improvement programs
 Continuous improvement programs conducted by my organization are buyer focused
 My organization has mechanisms for evaluating manufacturing processes
 Senior management has high involvement and support for continuous improvement programs
 My organization has a culture open to continuous improvements
 My organization has continuous improvement system which is integrated to strategic goals and objectives
 My organization follows best practices of continuous improvement available in the industry